

Refining the CTAB method for hyaluronic acid analysis: A cost-effective alternative to carbazole and LC-MS assays

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ABSTRACT

Reliable determination of hyaluronic acid (HA) in culture broth is critical for monitoring biotechnological production processes. Among the commonly used methods carbazole method is accessible but lacks specificity, while LC-MS offers high sensitivity but is costly and time-intensive. This study focuses on optimizing a benchtop turbidimetric assay using cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) for accurate and efficient HA quantification. Key reaction parameters, including concentrations of CTAB, NaOH, and NaCl, measurement conditions such as wavelength and time and the suitable method of capsular HA release were systematically optimized using standard HA solutions and culture broth samples. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis provided insights into the kinetics and mechanisms of HA-CTAB complex formation. The optimized CTAB protocol showed superior precision, accuracy, and resistance to interference compared to the carbazole assay, and exhibited strong concordance with LC-MS results. This refined CTAB method provides a cost-effective, practical, and robust solution for routine HA analysis in complex matrices.

1. Introduction

Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a high-value biopolymer widely used in pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications, with its production primarily reliant on microbial fermentation, particularly using *Streptococcus* species. HA is produced both extracellularly and as a capsular component tightly bound to bacterial cells. While sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) is conventionally used for releasing capsular HA (Blank et al., 2005b; Chen & Wang, 2009; Chong & Nielsen, 2003), alternative, less disruptive methods are of growing interest. Reliable quantification of HA in culture broth is essential for monitoring fermentation efficiency and optimizing production processes.

The most common method for HA quantification is the carbazole assay, which detects D-glucuronic acid following acidic hydrolysis. Despite its widespread use, this method suffers from significant interference by culture medium components such as saccharides, amino acids, and salts, which can yield false-positive signals (Bitter & Muir, 1962; Galambos, 1967; Song et al., 2009). Although sample purification steps (e.g., ethanol precipitation) can mitigate some of these issues (Chen & Wang, 2009; Murado et al., 2012; Song et al., 2009), the

method remains labor-intensive and susceptible to variability.

An alternative approach is the turbidimetric assay based on the interaction of the cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) with the polyanionic chain of HA in an alkaline environment and subsequent detection of a precipitated complex HA-CTAB. (Di Ferrante, 1956) This method offers higher specificity and allows direct measurement from culture broth without extensive purification. (Oueslati et al., 2014; Song et al., 2009). However, its application is limited by inconsistent protocols and potential interference from salts such as NaCl. Meanwhile, liquid chromatography (LC) coupled with the mass spectrometry (MS) detection remains the gold standard for HA quantification due to its high sensitivity and precision, although it is costly and requires enzymatic or non-enzymatic depolymerization before measurement. (Simek et al., 2020a).

Here, we optimized the CTAB assay for robust, accurate, and cost-effective quantification of HA in fermentation samples. We systematically examined critical parameters, including reagent concentrations (CTAB, NaOH, NaCl), detection wavelength, reaction time, and the effect of HA molecular weight. Novel aspects of the assay, such as freeze-thaw treatment for capsular HA release and the use of dynamic

Abbreviations: HA, hyaluronic acid; CTAB, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide; CV, coefficient of variation; LC-MS, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; Mw, molecular weight; SDS, sodium dodecyl-sulfate, RT, room temperature; DLS, dynamic light scattering.

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light scattering (DLS) to monitor HA-CTAB complex formation, were also investigated. The optimized protocol was benchmarked against the traditional carbazole method and LC-MS to assess its analytical performance and practical advantages. We hypothesized that systematic optimization of the CTAB turbidimetric assay, including reagent concentrations, detection parameters, and sample preparation methods, would yield a robust, cost-effective, and accurate alternative to the carbazole assay, with analytical performance comparable to LC-MS.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

HA of pharmaceutical grade and Mw of 0.013, 0.033, 0.17, 1.56, and 2.37 MDa was obtained from Contipro a.s. (Dolní Dobrouč, Czech Republic). Mw of HA was determined by SEC-MALLS (Čožíková et al., 2017).

Five culture broths, differing in the plant peptones used, were prepared by cultivation of *Streptococcus equi subs. zooepidemicus* (Contipro a.s., Dolní Dobrouč, Czech Republic). Cultivation media also contained sucrose, salts (MnCl₂·4H₂O, MgSO₄·7H₂O, Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O) and anti-foaming agent. *S. zooepidemicus* was cultivated at 37 °C, pH 7, 300 ml volume, 300 rpm, and for 16 h with aeration. Samples of peptones for cultivation were kindly provided by A. Costantino (Favria, Italy), all other used chemicals were purchased from Merck and Alchimica.

2.2. Initial CTAB assay condition

The CTAB assay was initially performed using a standard set of conditions, which were later modified to optimize individual parameters as described below. In this procedure, HA was diluted in acetic buffer (pH 6) containing 0.15 M NaCl to achieve the desired concentration. A 500 µl aliquot of HA solution was then mixed with equal volume of CTAB solution (25 mg ml⁻¹ in 2 % (w/v) NaOH). The mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 20 min, after which absorbance was measured at 600 nm using (Helios Epsilon, Thermo Scientific). These conditions, except for the detection wavelength, were based on those originally described by Di Ferrante, 1956. The acetic buffer (pH 6, with 0.15 M NaCl) was used as a blank in all experiments.

2.3. CTAB assay optimization

2.3.1. Optimization of reaction conditions of HA-CTAB complex formation

To determine a suitable calibration range, HA solutions were prepared across concentrations of 8.44 to 422 µg ml⁻¹ generating 21 calibration points. The effect of incubation temperature was evaluated by comparing reactions carried out at room temperature (RT) and 37 °C under otherwise identical conditions. Subsequent experiments focused on optimizing the concentrations of individual reagents.

HA samples (67.52 µg ml⁻¹) were incubated with CTAB at 10, 20, 30 or 40 µg ml⁻¹. Additional tests used HA (135.04 µg ml⁻¹) and CTAB at 10 or 25 mg ml⁻¹. The effects of NaOH concentration were investigated by preparing CTAB solutions in 0 %, 1 %, 2 %, 3 % and 4 % (w/v) NaOH, which were then reacted with HA (67.52 µg ml⁻¹). To evaluate the influence of ionic strength, HA was dissolved either with or without 0.15 M NaCl in the acetic buffer before mixing with CTAB (10 mg ml⁻¹ in 1 % (w/v) NaOH).

Reaction kinetics were assessed by incubating HA samples (33.76 and 101.28 µg ml⁻¹) with CTAB (10 µg ml⁻¹ in 1 % (w/v) NaOH) at RT and measuring absorbance every 10 min for 60 min at 400, 600 and 800 nm. These experiments aimed to determine the optimal reaction time and detection wavelength.

2.3.2. Sample preparation optimization

To evaluate suitable methods for removing cells from culture broth, samples were first diluted in acetic buffer (pH 6, no NaCl) to match the

calibration range. Two approaches were tested: (i) centrifugation at 13,400 rpm (working volume 2 ml, MiniSpin from Eppendorf) with collection of supernatant, and (ii) filtration through 0.2 and 0.45 µm syringe filters. The treated samples were then subjected to the CTAB assay using 10 µg ml⁻¹ in 1 % (w/v) NaOH, incubated at RT for 20 min and measured at 600 nm.

To evaluate the effectiveness of different methods for capsular HA release, two treatment approaches were compared using culture broth samples prepared with three different peptones. In the first approach sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) was added to culture broth to get final concentration of 0.05 % (w/v), the concentration typically used for capsular HA release. In the second approach, samples underwent a freeze-thaw cycle: they were frozen overnight at -20 °C and subsequently thawed at RT. All samples were diluted by acetic buffer (pH 6, without NaCl) to match the calibration range. Samples were then incubated for 20 min at RT with CTAB (10 µg ml⁻¹ in 1 % (w/v) NaOH) and measured immediately at 600 nm.

2.4. Final CTAB protocol

Samples of pure HA were diluted with pH 6 acetic buffer (with no added NaCl) to fit the calibration curve of 33.76 to 135.04 µg ml⁻¹. In case of culture broth, samples were treated by freeze-thaw cycle overnight at -20 °C and then diluted with pH 6 acetic buffer (without added NaCl) to fit the calibration range of 33.76 to 135.04 µg ml⁻¹. Samples were then centrifuged at 13 400 rpm (working volume 2 ml, MiniSpin, Eppendorf) to collect supernatant for the further steps.

Samples of both pure HA and culture broth supernatants were then mixed 1:1 with 10 mg ml⁻¹ CTAB in 1 % (w/v) NaOH solution in spectrophotometric cuvettes. Samples were incubated for 20 min at RT and absorbance was measured immediately at 600 nm. pH 6 acetic buffer was used as a blank.

2.5. DLS analysis

The dynamic light scattering was measured using Zetasizer Nano-ZS from Malvern Instruments equipped with a 633 nm He-Ne laser with backscattering detection at 25 °C. The samples consisted of 500 µl of 10 mg ml⁻¹ CTAB in 1 % (w/v) NaOH solution, 40 or 120 µl of 422 µg ml⁻¹ HA standard (1.56 MDa), and 460 or 380 µl of acetic buffer, with an overall volume of 1000 µl. After mixing the components, the measurements were started after 1 min of temperature equilibration. Ten measurements, each containing 11 runs with a duration of 10 s, were taken with a delay of 5 min between them. The differences between measurements were interpreted over time. The measurements were disturbed by the presence of aggregating particles. However, these processes are essential for investigated phenomena. Therefore, samples were not filtrated or diluted. The Z-average and polydispersity index were evaluated, when trends over time after mixing were interpreted rather than exact size. Data were processed using Zetasizer Software 7.11.

2.6. Effect of molecular weight of HA

Following Mw of HA 0.013, 0.033, 0.17, 1.56, and 2.37 MDa were used to prepare HA samples of 2.53, 3.38, 4.22 and 5.06 mg ml⁻¹. Samples were diluted 50-fold in acetic buffer (pH 6) to match the calibration range. The reaction was then carried out according to the modified basic protocol, i.e. NaCl was not used in acetic buffer, samples were incubated with CTAB of 10 µg ml⁻¹ in 1 % (w/v) NaOH at RT for 20 min and measured immediately after that at 600 nm.

2.7. Comparison of CTAB assay with carbazole and LC-MS method

To assess the precision and accuracy of the optimized CTAB assay, it was compared with the conventional carbazole assay. HA standards

(Mw 1.56 MDa) at concentrations 1.69, 2.53, 3.38, 4.22 and 5.06 mg ml⁻¹ prepared in acetic buffer (pH 6) were diluted 50-fold to match the calibration range. All samples were analysed using both the final CTAB protocol and the carbazole assay, as described below. The CTAB assay was subsequently benchmarked against LC-MS analysis to evaluate its analytical reliability.

To compare the robustness of the CTAB and carbazole methods under conditions that may interfere with assay accuracy, additional experiments were conducted using HA standards treated with common interfering substances. First, the effect of residual SDS was assessed by treating HA standards 1.69, 3.38 and 5.06 mg ml⁻¹ with 0.05 % (w/v) SDS. After subsequent dilution to match the calibration range, the residual SDS concentration was 0.008 %. These samples were analysed using both methods to determine their tolerance to surfactant interference.

Second, the influence of complex media components was evaluated by spiking HA standards (3.38, 4.22, and 5.06 mg ml⁻¹) with culture broth to final concentrations of 10 %, 25 % and 50 % (v/v). Following appropriate dilution, the samples were again analysed by both the CTAB and carbazole assays.

2.7.1. Carbazole assay protocol

Carbazole assay was used as described by Cesaretti et al. (2003). Briefly, standard solution of HA was used to prepare a calibration curve with 7 points in the range 16.88 – 101.28 µg ml⁻¹ of HA. Afterwards, 200 µl of the HA sample or standard was added to 1 ml of 25 mM sodium tetraborate in concentrated sulfuric acid. Samples were heated at 100 °C for 10 min and then cooled on ice for 5 min. Subsequently, 40 µl of 0.125 % carbazole in absolute ethanol was added to the reaction mixture and heated at 100 °C for 10 min and then cooled on ice for 5 min. Absorbance of the samples was then measured on the spectrophotometer at 550 nm with acetic buffer as a blank.

2.7.2. LC-MS analysis

Samples from cultivation broth were diluted 500-fold in 50 mM PBS containing 5 mM EDTA (pH 5). HA was quantified according to a previously validated method (Šimek et al., 2019). Briefly, a ¹³C-labelled HA internal standard (Contipro) and actinase E (Merck, Germany) were added to the samples to degrade proteins. Following enzymatic depolymerization of both native and ¹³C-labelled HA, the resulting disaccharides were analysed using an Acquity I-Class UPLC system equipped with a reversed-phase column and coupled to a mass spectrometer for detection.

3. Results and discussion

CTAB assay was chosen as a potentially cost-effective and reliable method for quantifying HA in complex biological matrices due to its high specificity and acceptable interferences with compounds of culture broth (Di Ferrante, 1956; Oueslati et al., 2014; Song et al., 2009). Impact of several key parameters of the CTAB assay on the analysis of HA was tested and optimized as described below. Furthermore, the resulting CTAB protocol was compared with carbazole assay and LC-MS for the analysis of the HA produced by fermentation.

3.1. Optimization of reaction conditions of HA-CTAB complex formation

Initial tests revealed non-linear absorbance behaviour across the tested concentration range of 8.27 to 413.5 µg ml⁻¹ (Fig. 1). A subrange of 33.76 to 135.04 µg ml⁻¹ provided a steeper response and more consistent signal-to-concentration ratio. This range was modelled using hyperbolic regression due to the non-linear behaviour observed. The non-linear response of CTAB assay is consistent with previous reports (Chen & Wang, 2009; Oueslati et al., 2014). Furthermore, lower limit of quantification was established 33.76 µg ml⁻¹ below which coefficient of variation values exceeded 20 % (Data not shown).

Fig. 1. Hyperbolic curve measured at 600 nm, equation of the curve and coefficient of determination are stated.

No significant difference in absorbance was observed between reactions incubated at 37 °C or at RT (data not shown). Incubation at both 37 °C (Chen & Wang, 2009; Di Ferrante, 1956; Oueslati et al., 2014) and RT (Song et al., 2009) is reported in the literature. For procedural simplicity, RT incubation was adopted for subsequent experiments. Concentration of CTAB reagent in the original procedure is 25 mg ml⁻¹ (Chen & Wang, 2009a; Di Ferrante, 1956; Oueslati et al., 2014). However, tests of various CTAB concentrations (10, 20, 25, 30 and 40 mg ml⁻¹) showed comparable signals as shown in Fig. 2 ($\alpha=0.05$). Therefore, the original assay used an unnecessary high excess of CTAB, which was further confirmed by analogous testing at highest concentration level (135.04 µg ml⁻¹) with identical results (Data not shown).

CTAB assay was previously done with 2 % NaOH solution (Di Ferrante, 1956; Oueslati et al., 2014; Song et al., 2009) or without NaOH (Chen & Wang, 2009; Hor et al., 2014; Shaheen et al., 2023). As there is scarce evidence of using different NaOH concentrations, impact of this parameter on the resulting absorbance was also tested. No difference in absorbance was observed between samples using 1 % NaOH and 2 %

Fig. 2. Determination of the CTAB concentration required for the reaction. The experiments were performed in five replicates with the HA sample at the concentration 67.52 µg ml⁻¹.

NaOH solution as shown in Fig. 3 ($\alpha=0.05$). It is obvious that the alkaline environment of the mixture plays crucial role for the HA-CTAB complex formation as absorbance of samples with no NaOH almost reached plateau above $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of HA (Data not shown). This supports the assumption that the carboxyl groups of HA must be negatively charged to allow interaction with the positively charged hydrophilic part of CTAB. Similar outcome was also observed by Oueslati et al. (2014), who tested the influence of different pH values of the HA solution. On the other hand, the use of a strongly alkaline solution may lead to higher solubility of HA-CTAB complex (Scott, 1960), which may explain the decreasing absorption at concentrations of 3 and 4 % of NaOH (see Fig. 3; significant at $\alpha=0.05$). For these reasons, further experiments were carried out with 1 % NaOH.

Another parameter affecting the CTAB assay is the molality of the reagent mixture. A common component of the acetic buffer used in CTAB-based assays is 0.15 M NaCl (Chen & Wang, 2009; Di Ferrante, 1956; Song et al., 2009). To assess its impact, the presence of NaCl in the reaction mixture was tested. It was found out that adding 0.15 M NaCl suppressed the reaction, with sample absorbance decreasing by 7.3 % compared to the NaCl-free sample (significant at $\alpha=0.05$; Fig. 4). This suppression aligns with previous observations that elevated salt concentrations (NaCl and KCl) suppress the formation of the HA-CTAB complex, with complete inhibition occurring at concentrations above 0.5 M (Oueslati et al., 2014). Similarly, Scott (1960) reported that increased ionic strength promotes dissolution of the HA-CTAB complex. Based on these findings, NaCl was excluded from buffer preparation in subsequent experiments.

Reaction time and measurement wavelength are critical parameters in the CTAB assay, as both vary across published protocols. Spectrophotometric measurements have commonly used either 400 nm (Chen & Wang, 2009; Di Ferrante, 1956) or 600 nm (Oueslati et al., 2014; Song et al., 2009) while reaction time differs between methods. In our study, we observed that turbidity does not develop immediately and changes over time. However, the change of absorbance over the time is not uniform across the tested wavelengths of 400, 600 and 800 nm. For instance, absorbance may increase at one wavelength (800 nm) while simultaneously decrease at another (400 nm), as shown in Fig. 5(a) and (b). These findings are consistent with previous reports. Oueslati et al. (2014) observed that turbidity was increasing during the first 5 min at

Fig. 3. Determination of the NaOH concentration required for the reaction. The differences in absorbances among samples with the different NaOH concentrations. The experiments were performed in five replicates using HA with a concentration of $67.52 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Fig. 4. Influence of NaCl on the reaction. HA samples with concentration $67.52 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ were tested in five replicates. NaCl concentration in the buffer was 0.15 M.

600 nm followed by a steady decline. Chen and Wang (2009) observed a continuous absorbance increase at 400 nm over a 14-minute period without any subsequent decrease across tested concentrations. Our results further show that absorbance increases toward lower wavelengths, in agreement with observations by Chen and Wang (2009).

Among the tested conditions, absorbance at 600 nm after 20 min reached the most stable plateau compared to 400 nm or 800 nm. Based on this, we selected 600 nm as the measurement wavelength and set the reaction time to 20 min for further experiments. Nevertheless, the measurement should be carried out immediately after the incubation to minimize variability.

To explore the processes underlying signal stability and wavelength-dependent behaviour, we employed dynamic light scattering (DLS). Z-average diameter and polydispersity index of particles created during HA precipitation by CTAB were determined at various times after mixing of precipitation components at two different HA concentrations (Fig. 6). The particles with a diameter of roughly 750 and 880 nm were determined in 2 min (the shortest determined time) after mixing at HA concentrations of $33.76 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and $101.28 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively. A gradual increase in particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) was determined with increasing time. This could be explained by progressive aggregation, coalescence, and Ostwald's ripening of created particles over time. The particles' instability disturbed DLS measurements through worsening data quality, unreliable exact diameter values, and too high PDI at longer times. However, general trends could still be interpreted and correlated with spectrophotometric measurements. The particle diameter was always larger for higher HA concentrations. Significantly higher HA concentration led to the formation of not only more but also larger particles at the same amount of CTAB. Also, more progressive aggregation was observed at higher HA concentration. Severe aggregation could cause sedimentation of larger objects, reducing overall particle concentration in the solution. This DLS evidence for progressive aggregation and sedimentation supports the selection of the 20-minute time point as the optimal measurement window, capturing the maximum turbidimetric signal just prior to the onset of severe particle settling. Based on these results, we hypothesize that sedimentation of particle aggregates could cause the decrease of absorbance determined in spectrophotometric measurements, mainly for higher HA concentration and shorter wavelengths. On the other hand, the absorbance at longer wavelengths could benefit more from the increased particle size with pronounced light scattering, mainly for lower HA concentration,

Fig. 5. Determination of the influence of reaction time and chosen wavelength. HA sample of $34 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (a) and $101 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (b) were measured at different wavelength. Similar results were obtained with two repetitions.

Fig. 6. Dependence of Z-average diameter and polydispersity index of $33.76 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and $101.28 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ on time after mixing determined using DLS.

where aggregation and probably sedimentation were not so severe.

3.2. Sample preparation optimization

Bacterial cells present in culture broth interfere with absorbance measurements at 600 nm due to their intrinsic turbidity. To address this, two cell removal strategies, centrifugation and filtration, were compared. Both approaches yielded comparable HA concentrations, and neither significantly affected assay results (Data not shown). No difference was observed between centrifugation times 5 and 20 min at 13,400 rpm, nor between filtration using 0.2 or $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ syringe filters. Given its speed and simplicity, centrifugation for 5 min was selected for the final protocol.

For capsular HA release, two cell-disruption strategies were evaluated: sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) treatment and freeze-thaw cycling. While methods like sonication or heat shock can degrade HA (Hafsa et al., 2017; Mondek et al., 2015), both SDS and freeze-thaw cycle were found to preserve intact HA. SDS treatment is widely reported for capsular HA release (Blank et al., 2005a; Chen & Wang, 2009; Chong & Nielsen, 2003), whereas freeze-thaw cycle has not been previously described in this context.

In our study, SDS treatment improved HA yield by 3.8, 10.9 and 10.6 % in three tested culture broths cultivated with different peptones, respectively, whereas freeze-thaw increased the yield by 1.9, 7.9 and 6.0

% (Table 1). Although SDS treatment was slightly more effective, the difference was not statistically significant ($\alpha=0.05$). The variability in yield likely reflects the influence of specific peptones on cellular behaviour.

Given the primary drawback of SDS, its tendency to cause significant foaming, freeze-thaw cycle presents a practical and cleaner alternative. Furthermore, it allows multiple short freeze-thaw cycles to be employed, potentially can enhancing HA release without compromising sample quality.

3.3. Effect of various molecular weight of HA

The suitability of methods for HA quantification is often influenced by the Mw of HA (Šimek et al., 2020b). To evaluate this effect, the optimized CTAB method was tested using HA samples of varying molecular weights to determine how Mw affects the resulting absorbance measurements. As shown in Fig. 7, no significant difference ($\alpha=0.05$) in absorbance was observed among samples of 0.17, 1.56 and 2.37 MDa. However, samples containing lower Mw HA (0.013 and 0.033 MDa) exhibited noticeably lower absorbance compared to the higher Mw samples. Furthermore, the 0.013 MDa sample showed lower absorbance than 0.033 MDa HA sample.

This Mw-dependent behaviour can be explained by the interaction mechanism between HA and CTAB. Scott (1960) observed that low-Mw HA fail to interact effectively with CTAB and remain dissolved in the ionic environment. This phenomenon becomes pronounced below 0.020 MDa and is of lesser importance above this threshold (Scott, 1960). The reduced absorbance observed for 0.033 MDa sample indicates the inherent polydispersity of HA samples, where a fraction of the molecules falls below the critical Mw threshold. In contrast, Oueslati (2014)

Table 1
Impact of SDS treatment on HA release.

	Fresh/without SDS		Fresh/with SDS		Freeze-thaw cycle	
	avg ^b (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV ^c (%)	avg ^b (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV ^c (%)	avg ^b (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV ^c (%)
Pepton A ^a	4.76	3.56	4.94	3.27	4.85	2.20
Pepton B ^a	4.95	2.85	5.49	3.29	5.34	2.93
Pepton C ^a	4.83	2.83	5.34	3.80	5.12	3.76

^a samples from cultivations based on different peptones type were tested.

^b average recovery (mg ml⁻¹) of nine measurements, each sample was prepared in triplicate and measured in three repetitions.

^c coefficient of variation of repeated measurements (%).

Fig. 7. Influence of Mw of HA on the absorbance. Experiments were performed in triplicate for five different concentrations of HA samples. Only concentrations of 2.53 and 5.06 mg ml⁻¹ are shown as the other concentrations provided us with comparable result.

reported that HA-CTAB complex formation is independent on Mw when working exclusively with fragments above 0.070 MDa. This finding supports the critical role of Mw in the CTAB assay performance. These results have important implications for HA quantification using the CTAB method. When measuring low-Mw HA samples, it is essential to select calibration standards with appropriate molecular weights that match the sample characteristics to ensure accurate quantification.

Finally, non-linear behaviour in CTAB method was observed. It was found out, that it is beneficial not to add 0.15 M NaCl into acetic buffer. Sufficient concentration of reagents was stated as 10 mg ml⁻¹ CTAB in 1 % NaOH. The reaction time was set to 20 min, and it was necessary to measure all samples immediately after that to minimize bias. The suitable wavelength for CTAB method was 600 nm. Additionally, it was observed, that it is problematic to determine HA of lower Mw, i.e. <0.030 MDa. Centrifugation is a sufficient method for bacterial cells removal, and it is possible to replace SDS treatment by freezing cells overnight and subsequently thaw them.

In summary, the CTAB assay was optimized by omitting 0.15 M NaCl from the buffer, using 10 mg ml⁻¹ CTAB in 1 % NaOH, and measuring absorbance at 600 nm after 20 min. Centrifugation is sufficient for removing cells, and freeze-thaw cycles offer a simple alternative to SDS for HA release, streamlining the protocol without affecting yield or sample quality.

3.4. Comparison of CTAB method with carbazole assay

Following optimization of the CTAB assay reaction conditions, the final CTAB protocol was compared with the established carbazole assay.

Table 2

Comparison of results for CTAB and carbazole method.

	concentration of HA standards	intraday repeatability						interday repeatability			
		c (mg ml ⁻¹)						acc.			
		day 1		day 2		day 3		day 1		day 2	day 3
		c (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV	c (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV	c (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV	c (mg ml ⁻¹)	CV	acc.	
carbazole	1.69	1.41 ± 0.03	1.86 ± 0.08	1.78 ± 0.03	83.8	110.2	105.5	1.69 ± 0.24	14.09	99.8	
	2.53	2.35 ± 0.01	2.86 ± 0.01	2.35 ± 0.19	92.7	112.8	92.8	2.52 ± 0.29	11.65	99.4	
	3.38	3.46 ± 0.09	3.87 ± 0.02	3.18 ± 0.03	102.6	114.7	94.3	3.51 ± 0.35	9.88	103.9	
	4.22	4.24 ± 0.05	4.96 ± 0.05	4.46 ± 0.37	100.5	117.5	105.6	4.55 ± 0.37	8.07	107.9	
	5.06	5.16 ± 0.1	5.93 ± 0.11	5.3 ± 0.03	101.8	117.1	104.7	5.46 ± 0.41	7.53	107.9	
CTAB	1.69	1.69 ± 0	1.61 ± 0.02	1.69 ± 0.06	100.1	95.2	100.1	1.66 ± 0.05	2.87	98.4	
	2.53	2.52 ± 0.02	2.51 ± 0.02	2.49 ± 0.08	99.6	99.0	98.5	2.51 ± 0.01	0.55	99.1	
	3.38	3.49 ± 0.04	3.34 ± 0.01	3.38 ± 0.1	103.5	99.0	100.0	3.4 ± 0.08	2.34	100.8	
	4.22	4.17 ± 0.08	4.28 ± 0.08	4.22 ± 0.07	98.8	101.5	100.0	4.22 ± 0.06	1.35	100.1	
	5.06	5.01 ± 0.06	4.95 ± 0.02	5 ± 0.07	98.9	97.7	98.7	4.99 ± 0.03	0.66	98.5	

^aconcentration of HA standards (mg ml⁻¹).

^baverage recovery (%) of six measurements performed as duplicates in three days.

^ccoefficient of variation from repeated measurements.

Both methods were evaluated for precision and accuracy using pure HA samples, followed by assessment of potential interferences from SDS and culture media components that are commonly encountered during bacterial cell processing after cultivation. In intraday repeatability testing, the CTAB assay demonstrated superior performance compared to the carbazole method across both accuracy and precision metrics. Recovery values for the CTAB assay ranged from 95.2 to 103.5 %, substantially tighter than the 83.8 to 117.5 % range observed for the carbazole method (Table 2). The CTAB assay's precision was notably superior, with coefficients of variation (CV) between 0.01 and 3.76 % compared to 0.31 to 8.22 % for the carbazole assay. Interday repeatability testing revealed similar advantages: the CTAB method achieved recovery values of 98.4 to 100.8 % (versus 99.8 to 107.9 % for carbazole) and CVs of 0.55 to 2.87 % (versus 7.53 to 14.09 % for carbazole). Interestingly, carbazole assay deteriorated more rapidly at lower concentrations than the CTAB assay, suggesting that carbazole assay was approaching its limit of quantification. These findings are consistent with those of Chen and Wang (2009), who also reported better precision for the CTAB method, although they did not evaluate accuracy.

SDS solution is routinely used for capsular HA release at concentration of 0.05 % in presence of cells at RT for 10 min (Blank et al., 2005b; Chen & Wang, 2009; Chong & Nielsen, 2003). Given the potential interaction between SDS and CTAB due to their opposite charges and surfactant properties (Tah et al., 2011), the effect of SDS on both assays was tested. The CTAB assay showed minimal sensitivity to SDS interference, samples with added SDS exhibited slightly lower absorbance compared to samples without SDS (Table 3). In contrast, the carbazole assay demonstrated significant sensitivity to SDS presence ($p <$

Table 3
Influence of SDS on HA-CTAB complex formation and on carbazole reaction.

Concentration of HA standards ^a	CTAB method			Carbazole method		
	Without SDS	0.05 % SDS		Without SDS	0.05 % SDS	
		acc (%) ^b	CV ^d		acc (%) ^b	CV ^d
1.69	96.06	92.88	1.37	99.87	41.46	12.20
3.38	98.44	93.05	2.83	98.79	46.90	9.72
5.06	98.37	94.29	1.40	100.67	47.96	3.19

^a concentration of HA standards (mg ml⁻¹).

^b recovery (%) of single measurement determined by the CTAB or carbazole.

^c recovery (%) measurements in triplicate determined by the CTAB or carbazole.

^d coefficient of variation (%) from repeated measurements.

0.05). Samples with SDS showed markedly lower absorbance than those without SDS (Table 3), indicating, that SDS suppresses the carbazole-HA reaction. Therefore, SDS removal is essential before HA determination using the carbazole assay, whereas our CTAB method is immune to SDS interference.

The influence of standard culture broth components on both assays was evaluated because cultivation media represents a complex matrix that could potentially interfere with HA quantification, and understanding this interference is crucial for selecting appropriate analytical approaches for bacterial HA production studies. The CTAB assay showed no statistically significant interference from culture media at any tested dilution ($\alpha = 0.05$), as demonstrated in Table 4.

Conversely, the carbazole assay exhibited substantial interference from culture media components at all tested dilutions, with absorbance increasing nearly 10-fold at 50 % media dilution (Data not shown). This interference was visually apparent, with media-containing samples displaying a dark pink colour compared to the light pink colour of media-free samples.

While the CTAB assay is generally resistant to media interference, complete immunity should not be assumed. Oueslati et al. (2014) observed that CTAB reactions in BHI media with elevated salt content (0.125 M) showed suppressed HA-CTAB complex formation. This consideration is important when analysing high salt samples, and this also support our finding that the omission of NaCl addition supports HA-CTAB complex formation as shown in Section 3.1.

The interference of cultivation media with carbazole reaction is well documented (Bitter & Muir, 1962; Galambos, 1967; Oueslati, 2014; Song et al., 2009) and is likely caused by carbazole interaction with sugars, proteins, amino acids, chlorides, or other culture broth components. Even residual amounts of culture media remaining after cultivation can cause significant inaccuracy in HA determination. Therefore, contaminant removal through HA precipitation using ethanol or

Tab 4
Effect of culture media addition on observed HA concentration values when using CTAB or carbazole assay was examined.

CTAB method								
Concentration of HA standards ^a	Without SDS		10 % (v/v)		25 % (v/v)		50 % (v/v)	
	acc ^b	CV ^c						
3.38	91.09	4.44	97.48	2.63	95.05	1.85	92.93	2.93
4.22	96.95	2.43	95.33	3.95	98.34	2.74	95.89	1.48
5.06	98.04	2.36	94.52	2.90	97.57	1.67	96.05	1.67
Carbazole method								
Concentration of HA standards ^a	Without SDS		10 % (v/v)		25 % (v/v)		50 % (v/v)	
	acc ^b	CV ^c						
3.38	96.92	6.79	235.28	2.05	401.48	2.45	635.50	3.59
4.22	97.25	3.57	206.25	4.49	322.19	0.95	510.86	5.26
5.06	95.13	3.49	182.72	4.94	298.94	3.69	451.67	5.42

^a concentration of HA standards (mg ml⁻¹).

^b recovery (%) of three measurements determined by the CTAB or carbazole.

^c coefficient of variation (%) from repeated measurements.

isopropanol is necessary when using the carbazole method, while the CTAB method does not require this step.

3.5. Comparison of CTAB method with LC-MS

The determination of HA concentration by the CTAB method was compared with results obtained by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS). LC-MS is considered the gold standard for HA quantification due to its high specificity, immunity to matrix interferences, and exceptional sensitivity. However, the widespread adoption of LC-MS is limited by high cost the need for specialized equipment and expertise, and pricy (¹³C-labelled standard) and time-consuming sample preparation (>2 h) requiring depolymerization steps (Simek et al., 2020).

The linearity of all three analytical methods (CTAB, carbazole, and LC-MS) was evaluated and is presented in Fig. 8. All methods exhibited comparable linear responses within the tested concentration range, confirming that the optimized CTAB assay provides a reliable quantitative relationship between HA concentration and analytical signal. As summarized in Table 5, the optimized CTAB method showed excellent agreement with LC-MS results. The CTAB method demonstrated high precision with coefficients of variation ranging from 0.94 % to 2.67 %, while LC-MS achieved superior precision ($p = 0.01$) with CV values of 0.15 % to 1.07 %. Both methods showed excellent accuracy: CTAB recovery ranged from 98.4 % to 100.8 %, comparable to LC-MS recovery of 98–101 % (previously validated, data not shown). The limit of quantification (LOQ) for the CTAB method was not formally determined; however, recovery of the QC sample at the lowest point of the calibration curve was evaluated in triplicate and ranged from 94.5 % to 105 %, indicating adequate performance at low concentrations. In contrast, the previously validated LC-MS method has an LOQ of 0.2 µg/mL (data not shown).

Although LC-MS offers better precision, the CTAB method provides adequate accuracy and precision for routine HA analysis while offering significant practical advantages: simpler sample preparation, faster analysis time, and substantially lower costs, requiring only a UV detector versus expensive LC-MS instrumentation.

Despite its advantages, the CTAB assay also has several limitations compared with conventional analytical techniques. The method shows lower sensitivity than LC-MS assay, making it more suitable for samples containing moderate to high concentrations of HA, such as fermentation broths. Additionally, because turbidity depends on the aggregation and sedimentation behavior of CTAB-HA particles, consistent timing of absorbance measurements is essential to ensure reproducible results. These limitations should be considered when selecting the most appropriate analytical approach for a given application.

Fig. 8. Linearity comparison of the CTAB, carbazole, and LC-MS methods for HA quantification.

Table 5

Comparison of CTAB method and LC-MS method.

sample ^a	c (mg ml ⁻¹) ^b		difference (%) ^c	CV (%) ^d	
	CTAB	LC-MS		CTAB	LC-MS
1	2.93 ± 0.04	2.81 ± 0.01	4.40	1.23	0.41
2	4.58 ± 0.12	4.47 ± 0.02	2.50	2.67	0.43
3	2.77 ± 0.05	2.91 ± 0.03	-4.91	1.85	1.07
4	3.56 ± 0.07	3.69 ± 0.01	-3.48	1.94	0.15
5	3.69 ± 0.03	3.72 ± 0.02	-0.81	0.94	0.48

^a five samples from culture broths obtained by cultivation with different peptones.

^b average concentration of HA (mg ml⁻¹) ± standard deviation from five measurements determined by CTAB method or LC-MS.

^c percentage difference between concentrations evaluated by CTAB method and LC-MS.

^d coefficient of variation (%) from repeated measurements.

4. Conclusion

This study presents a thoroughly optimized turbidimetric CTAB assay for the quantification of hyaluronic acid in complex fermentation samples. By systematically evaluating and refining key reaction parameters, we developed a protocol that is more specific, reproducible, and environmentally sustainable than the conventional carbazole assay. Key improvements include the exclusion of NaCl, reduced CTAB and NaOH concentrations, and a defined reaction time of 20 min with absorbance measured at 600 nm making the assay cheaper, less laborious, and also more environmentally friendly.

Importantly, our results demonstrate that a freeze-thaw cycle is a viable alternative to SDS treatment for capsular HA release, simplifying sample preparation while maintaining analytical accuracy. DLS analysis provided insight into the kinetics and mechanisms of HA-CTAB complex formation.

Compared to the carbazole assay, the optimized CTAB method offers superior precision, sensitivity, and resistance to matrix interference, making it more suitable for routine HA analysis in culture broth. Furthermore, the assay shows strong concordance with LC-MS measurements, confirming its validity as a reliable benchtop alternative for HA quantification.

In conclusion, the CTAB assay optimized in this study bridges the gap between low-cost simplicity and high analytical performance, offering a valuable tool for both research and industrial monitoring of hyaluronic acid production.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Kristýna Svobodová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Matěj Šimek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jana Jílková:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **František Ondřej:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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